

Integration of single-cell RNA-Seq and CyTOF data characterises heterogeneity of rare cell
subpopulations
Supplementary Table

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Table 1: Comparisons of the ARI and F1 scores for alternative options for the anchor finding and data transferring steps of the integration. F1 score equal to 0 signifies no predicted cells for this population.

Analysis name	Options tested differently to the Main analysis	F1										
		ARI	B	CD4	CD8	cMono	DC	GDT	MAIT	ncMono	NK	PB
Main analysis	NA	0.832	0.996	0.929	0.798	0.967	0.393	0.586	0.771	0.860	0.949	0.989
Analysis1	rpca in FindTransferAnchors	0.804	0.995	0.918	0.766	0.963	0.412	0.576	0.729	0.839	0.931	0.988
Analysis2	pcaproject in FindTransferAnchors	0.744	0.996	0.887	0.648	0.941	0.000	0.585	0.719	0.853	0.889	0.007
Analysis3	cca in TransferData	0.509	0.938	0.738	0.735	0.823	0.165	0.308	0.401	0.695	0.818	0.704
Analysis4	pcaproject in FindTransferAnchors and pcaproject in TransferData	0.348	0.933	0.485	0.583	0.793	0.000	0.733	0.496	0.766	0.545	0.000
Analysis5	non-integrated PCA of the scRNA-Seq for the weigth reduction in TransferData	0.798	0.996	0.912	0.732	0.964	0.398	0.132	0.206	0.827	0.940	0.993